

Challenges in avoiding deep-water shark bycatch in Azorean hook-and-line fisheries

Laurence Fauconnet ^{1,2},
José Manuel Gonzalez-Irusta ^{1,2}

¹Institute of Marine Sciences—Okeanos, University of the Azores, 9901-862 Horta, Portugal

²IMAR—Instituto do Mar, University of the Azores, 9901-862 Horta, Portugal

³Instituto Español de Oceanografía, Centro Oceanográfico de Santander (COST-IEO), CSIC, Promontorio San Martín, s/n Aptdo. 240 39080 Santander, Spain

*Corresponding author: tel: (+351) 292 200 400; e-mail: laurence.fauconnet@gmail.com.

Deep-water sharks are highly diverse, vulnerable, and understudied as a group, despite the increasing pressures on their populations. Twenty-five species of deep-water sharks have been recorded in the Azores, an oceanic archipelago in the mid-North Atlantic, that are regularly caught as bycatch in hook-and-line fisheries. Avoiding the bycatch of deep-water sharks presents multiple challenges due to their high catchability, difficulties in correctly identifying species, and the general lack of data on these species. This review summarizes the findings of recent studies from the region, providing an up-to-date science-based framework for mitigating bycatch effects of Azorean hook-and-line fisheries. Several depth-based, area-based, and gear-based measures have been studied that demonstrate the potential to either avoid or increase the survival of deep-water shark bycatch. However, these measures may have limited efficacy for some species (e.g. highly mobile species) and thus, limited widespread applicability. Convincing fishers to avoid deep-water shark bycatch is also a challenge given the antagonistic interactions with sharks damaging the catch and fishing gear, while simultaneously a market incentive for shark liver oil remains. It highlights the need to proactively engage fishers and incentivize the mitigation of bycatch of deep-water sharks in Azorean waters.

Keywords: bycatch avoidance, data-poor, deep-water longlines, elasmobranchs, prohibited species.

Introduction

Human pressures on the deep sea have increased greatly in recent decades raising concerns about the conservation of this ecosystem and its inhabitants (Barbier *et al.*, 2014). With the expansion of fisheries into progressively deeper waters (Morato *et al.*, 2006; Norse *et al.*, 2012; Victorero *et al.*, 2018), deep-water sharks—defined as elasmobranchs that live or spend most of their life cycle at depths >200 m—have been increasingly exposed to fishing pressures (Akhilesh *et al.*, 2011; Rincon *et al.*, 2017), either directly (Perrotta, 2004; Hareide *et al.*, 2007) or indirectly (Correia and Smith, 2004; Pajuelo *et al.*, 2010; Moura *et al.*, 2018; Fauconnet *et al.*, 2019a). The indirect catch of deep-water sharks while targeting other species is hereafter referred to as bycatch or unwanted catch.

Deep-water sharks are characterized by life-history traits such as slow growth, late maturity, and low fecundity, that makes them some of the most vulnerable species to fishing (Simpfendorfer and Kyne, 2009), even with low fishing mortality rates (Garcia *et al.*, 2008). Management measures aiming to avoid unwanted catch and increase survival of deep-water sharks are necessary to mitigate their bycatch and improve their population status, as has been requested by the North East Atlantic Fisheries Commission (NEAFC) and Oslo Paris Commission (OSPAR) to the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES, 2020a). Although further studies are still required, there has been a substantial contribution to this knowledge base in the last decade through

testing operational and technical solutions to manage the bycatch problem. This paper reviews recent studies from the Azores archipelago on reducing unwanted catch and mortality of deep-water sharks, in addition to highlighting the numerous challenges in incentivizing the avoidance of this bycatch and discusses ways forward.

Deep-water sharks, fisheries, and management challenges in the Azores

The study of deep-water chondrichthyans has evolved significantly over the last several decades, but fundamental biological, ecological, and behavioural information is still lacking for most species (Norse *et al.*, 2012; Cotton and Grubbs, 2015). In the Azores (Figure 1), 25 species of deep-water sharks have been recorded to date (Das and Afonso, 2017; Fauconnet *et al.*, 2020) ranging from a maximum size of about 28 cm (e.g. spined pygmy shark *Squaliolus laticaudus*) to 640 cm (Greenland shark *Somniosus microcephalus*; Figure 2). All deep-water shark species occurring in the Azores have late onset of sexual maturity. The length at first maturity ranges from 56 to 89% of maximum length for females in 22 species (three species unknown), and 47 to 90% for males in 23 species (two unknown; Figure 3; Table 1; Fauconnet *et al.*, 2020). All species of deep-water sharks occurring in the Azores are viviparous with yolk-sac, a reproductive mode typical of K-strategy species, except for the Iceland catshark (*Apristurus laurussonii*) and mouse catshark (*Galeus murinus*) that are

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Figure 1. Map of the Azores Exclusive Economic Zone. Source: adapted from Das *et al.*, 2022.

Figure 2. Mean preferred depths of occurrence of the deep-water shark species of the Azores, with size of icons proportional to the maximum species total length, and colour coded according to species known abundance in the Azores. Species codes: APR *Apristurus laurussonii*; ARR *Zameus squamulosus*; AZO *Scymnodalatias garricki*; BRR *Centrophorus granulosus*; CLA *C. anguineus*; COL *Centroscymnus coelolepis*; CRY *Centroscymnus owstonii*; FAB *Centroscyllium fabricii*; GAT *Dalatias licha*; GLD *S. microcephalus*; GMU *G. murinus*; HEP *Hepranchias perlo*; HEX *H. griseus*; LIX1 *Etmopterus spinax*; LIX2 *Etmopterus pusillus*; LIX3 *Etmopterus princeps*; OXY *Oxyntotus paradoxus*; PSE *Pseudotriakis microdon*; RIN *Scymnodon ringens*; SAP1 *Deania calcea*; SAP2 *Deania profundorum*; SAP3 *Centroscymnus crepidater*; SOM *Somniosus rostratus*; SQU *S. laticaudus*; XAR *Centrophorus squamosus*. Source: adapted from Fauconnet *et al.* 2020.

oviparous. However, oviparity is not associated with many offspring in these species as only a maximum of six eggs are laid in each clutch, and the mouse catshark *G. murinus* sometimes only produces two eggs (Iglesias *et al.*, 2002). Litter size is also small for most viviparous species (unknown for three

species), averaging between 2 and 20 pups per litter, except for the bluntnose sixgill shark (*Hexanchus griseus*) that produces an average litter size of 78 pups (Table 1). The gestation period is not yet known for most species (21 species out of 25) but, when known, ranges between 1 year to up to 3.5 years

Figure 3. Maximum total length (gray bars) and length at first maturity for males (blue lines) and for females (red lines) reported in the literature of all species of deep-water sharks occurring in the Azores. Species ordered from the smallest to the largest maximum total length. Data sources as indicated in Table 1.

in the case of the frilled shark (*Chlamydoselachus anguineus*; Tanaka *et al.*, 1990; Table 1). The best available information, although limited, confirms that life-history traits (late onset of sexual maturity, long gestation period, low fertility, viviparity, k-reproductive strategy, long life expectancy) exacerbate the vulnerability of deep-water sharks to exploitation by fisheries.

The Azores archipelago, lacking a continental shelf and with great depths surrounding the islands, has a long history of fisheries exploiting deep-sea species (Menezes, 1996; Morato *et al.*, 2002; Diogo *et al.*, 2015), including deep-water sharks (Figure 4). From the 1970s to the late 1990s, kitefin shark (*D. licha*) was targeted by Azorean fishers (Perrotta, 2004) primarily to exploit squalene, a high-value compound used in the cosmetic and pharmaceutical industries, found in high concentrations in the liver of deep-water sharks (Remme *et al.*, 2006). Traditionally, the fishery was artisanal, operated by small boats using vertical handlines, at depths of 70–200 m. In the mid-1980s, the fishery expanded, joined by a large fleet of cabin-deck vessels using gillnets (Perrotta, 2004), fishing at similar, but also deeper depths. Interestingly, there was a marked difference in size and sex selectivity between the handlines and gillnets, with larger, female specimens being more frequently caught (85% of total catch) on handlines, that fish shallower, compared to bottom gillnets (25%; Silva, 1987). The number of females was indeed found to decrease at 300–480 m, depth range at which males are more numerous than females (Silva, 1987). During the 1980s, kitefin shark was the deep-water fish species caught in largest volumes in the region, with kitefin shark landings contributing 19% of the total fisheries catch from the Azores (Silva, 1987; Machado *et al.*, 2004; Perrotta, 2004). Following market fluctuations, landings oscillated considerably over the period 1981–1991, peaking at 937 t in 1984 and 896 t in 1991 (ICES, 2015). A combination of high exploitation, decrease in abundance and competition from foreign markets resulted in the decline of

the commercial value of shark liver oil in the early 1990s, and eventually the end of the kitefin shark fishery in 1998 (Perrotta, 2004). A classic case of boom-and-bust fishing, the history of the kitefin fishery in the Azores was considered an “example and warning when implementing elasmobranchs fisheries management” in other parts of the world (Perrotta, 2004).

Deep-water sharks continue to be commonly caught as bycatch in the Azorean demersal and deep-sea hook-and-line fisheries (Pham *et al.*, 2013; Fauconnet *et al.*, 2019a; Figure 5), particularly in the bottom longlines and handlines fishery targeting deep-water teleosts, such as the blackspot seabream (*Pagellus bogaraveo*), alfonosinos (*Beryx spp.*), and Blackbelly rosefish (*Helicolenus dactylopterus*) (Pham *et al.*, 2013; Fauconnet *et al.*, 2019a). The latter is the dominant Azorean fishery in terms of number of fishing vessels, number of fishers, and landed value (Carvalho, 2010). The bycatch of deep-water sharks in the bottom longline and handline fishery is estimated to amount to 223 t per year, representing 4.9% of the total catch of the fishery (Fauconnet *et al.*, 2019a). Commonly bycaught deep-water shark species include several species categorised as Threatened in the European IUCN Red List (Nieto *et al.*, 2015) such as the Critically Endangered gulper shark (*C. granulosus*), the leafscale gulper shark (*C. squamosus*), kitefin shark (*D. licha*), and birdbeak dogfish (*D. calcea*), all three listed as Endangered in the IUCN Red List (Figure 5). Other bycaught species include lanternsharks, like the Near-Threatened velvet belly (*E. spinax*), the bluntnose sixgill shark (*H. griseus*, Least Concern), the arrowhead dogfish (*D. profundorum*), and other Data Deficient species (Figure 5) that may be potentially threatened (Walls and Dulvy, 2020). Additionally, deep-water sharks were the main bycatch of an experimental drifting longline fishery targeting black scabbardfish that operated in the Azores between 1998 to 2016 (Machete *et al.*, 2011). The fishery caught 19 tonnes of deep-water sharks

Table 1. Biological and ecological information available for the 25 species of deep-water sharks recorded to date in the Azores EEZ.

ORDER / Family / Species	Common Name	Occurrence	L0(cm)	Lm_F(cm)	Lm_M(cm)	Lmax(cm)	Longevity (years)	Reproductive strategy	Litter size	Gestation period (years)	Depth range (m)	IUCN
HEXANCHIFORMES												
Cladoselachidae												
<i>C. anguineus</i>	Friilled shark	R	39–60	126–150 ¹	118	196	n.a.	Viv.	2–15 (6)	3.5 ²	120–1 450 (17–1520)	LC
Hexanchidae												
<i>H. perlo</i>	Sharpnose sevengill shark	I	26 ³	90–105 ¹	75–85	139	n.a.	Viv.	6–20	n.a.	27–720 (1 000 max)	DD
<i>H. griseus</i>	Bluntnose sixgill shark	I	61–74	400	310–330	482	n.a.	Viv.	47–108	n.a.	200–1 100 (2 500 max)	LC
CARCHARHINIFORMES												
Pentanchidae												
<i>A. laurussonii</i>	Iceland catshark	R	25	59	68	76	n.a.	Ovi.	6	n.a.	560–2 060	LC
<i>G. murinus</i>	Mouth catshark	R	8–9 ⁴	46 ⁴	50–63	63	n.a.	Ovi.	2–6	n.a.	380–1 300	LC
Pseudotriakidae												
<i>P. microdon</i>	False catshark	I	120 ⁵	265	260	296	n.a.	Voo.	2	n.a.	500–1 440 (100–2 430)	DD
SQUALIFORMES												
Centrophoridae												
<i>C. granulatus</i>	Gulper shark	C	30–47	138–150	105–118 ⁶	176	39(F); 25(M)	Viv.	1–13	n.a.	600–1 500 (50–1 500)	CR
<i>C. squamosus</i>	Leafscale gulper shark	C	30–40	110–125	100–110	166	72	Viv.	5–8	n.a.	1 000–1 300 (0–3 370)	EN
<i>D. calcea</i>	Birdbeak dogfish	C	28–34	94–106	73–94	162	35 ⁷	Viv.	1–17 (7)	n.a.	400–900 (60–1 504)	EN
<i>D. profundorum</i>	Arrowhead dogfish	C	27 ⁸	62–80	43–67	97	29	Viv.	5–7	n.a.	450–1 050 (205–1 800)	DD
Dalatiidae												
<i>D. licha</i>	Kitefin shark	C	30–40	120	100	182	15	Viv.	3–16 (6–8)	2 ⁹	200–1 800 (37–1 800)	EN
<i>S. laticaudus</i>	Spined pygmy shark	I	8–10	17–20	15	28	n.a.	Viv.	3–5	n.a.	500–1 200 (200 min*)	LC
Etmopteridae												
<i>C. fabricii</i>	Black dogfish	I	15–20	50–70	46–63	107	n.a.	Viv.	4–40 (16)	n.a.	275–2250 (180–2250) ¹⁰	LC
<i>E. princeps</i>	Great lanternshark	I	12–17	62	57	94 ¹¹	n.a.	Viv.	7–18 (10)	n.a.	350–2213 (350–4500)	LC
<i>E. pusillus</i>	Smooth lanternshark	C	15–16	38–47	31–39	50	17(F); 13(M)	Viv.	1–6 (3.5)	n.a.	400–700 (0–2000)	DD
<i>E. spinax</i>	Velvet belly	C	8–14	30–41	24–35	55	11(F); 8(M) ¹²	Viv.	1–21	1	200–500 (70–2490)	NT

Table 1. Continued

ORDER / Family / Species	Common Name	Occurrence	L0(cm)	Lm_F(cm)	Lm_M(cm)	Lmax(cm)	Longevity (years)	Reproductive strategy	Litter size	Gestation period (years)	Depth range (m)	IUCN
Oxymotidae												
<i>O. paradoxus</i>	Sailfin roughshark	R	25	n.a	75	118	n.a.	Viv.	n.a.	n.a.	265–720	DD
Somniosidae												
<i>C. coelelepis</i>	Portuguese dogfish	C	23–35	92–102	75–85	130	n.a.	Viv.	1–29 (12–14)	> 2 ¹³	400–3 400 (128–3 675)	EN
<i>C. crepidater</i>	Longnose velvet dogfish	C	28–35	77–88	60–68	105	54(F); 34(M)	Viv.	1–9 (6)	n.a.	1030–1 240 (200–2 080)	LC
<i>C. oustonii</i>	Roughskin dogfish	C	25–35	82–105	67–84	120	n.a.	Viv.	5–34	n.a.	600–990 (150–1 460) ¹⁰	n.a (VU)
<i>S. garricki</i>	Azores dogfish	R	n.a	n.a	n.a	40.6+	n.a.	n.a	n.a.	n.a.	300–580+	DD
<i>S. ringens</i>	Knifetooth dogfish	R	n.a	n.a	n.a	110	n.a.	Viv. (prob.)	n.a.	n.a.	200–1 600	LC
<i>S. microcephalus</i>	Greenland shark	R	40–50	450	300	640	n.a.	Viv.	7–10	n.a.	0–1 400 (2 650 max)	NT
<i>S. rostratus</i>	Little sleeper shark	R	21–28	80	71	143	n.a.	Viv.	6–17	n.a.	180–2 734	DD
<i>Z. squamulosus</i>	Velvet dogfish	I	20	59–69	47–51	84	n.a.	Viv.	3–10	n.a.	550–1 511	DD

Sources: biological and depth data from Ebert *et al.* (2021a), unless specified; longevity data accessed from FishBase on 17 February 2022, as “species ecology matrix” by family, unless specified. ¹(Barnett *et al.*, 2012); ²(Tanaka *et al.*, 1990); ³(Basusta, 2016); ⁴(Iglesias *et al.*, 2002); ⁵(Yano, 1992); ⁶(White *et al.*, 2013); ⁷(Clarke *et al.*, 2002b); ⁸(Sousa *et al.*, 2009); ⁹(Silva, 1988); ¹⁰(Porteiro *et al.*, 2017); ¹¹(Cotton *et al.*, 2015); ¹²(Coelho and Erzini, 2008b); ¹³(Veríssimo *et al.*, 2011). Taxonomy following Catalogue of life (<https://www.catalogueoflife.org/>, accessed on 22 February 2022). n.a. = unknown/not available. The occurrence of the species is primarily based on occurrence in demersal scientific fishing surveys and observer data on-board bottom longlines fishing vessels; R = rare; I = infrequent; C = common; L0 = total length (or range of lengths) at t0 (birth) in cm; Lm_F = total length (or range of lengths) at maturity of females in cm; Lm_M = total length (or range of lengths) at maturity of males in cm; Lmax = maximum (known to date) total length in cm; F = female; M = male; reproductive strategy: Viv. = viviparous with oophagy; Ovi. = oviparous with oophagy; Prob. = probably; litter size in number (or range of numbers) of pups/eggs; in parentheses average number; depth range = preferred and full/maximum depth range in parentheses; *at night time; + = only based on two specimens; IUCN = European IUCN Red List of Threatened Species status from Nieto *et al.* (2015); DD = Data Deficient, LC = Least Concern, NT = Near Threatened, VU = Vulnerable, EN = Endangered, CR = Critically Endangered; in parenthesis Global Status from Finucci & Kyne (2018).

Figure 4. Catch of deep-water sharks in the Azores for the last five decades (1970–2018). Values include the fishery targeting kitefin shark (*D. licha*), the bottom trawl experiments carried out in 2001–2002, and the deep-water hook-and-line fisheries. It compares official landings (grey bars) and estimated unreported catch including discards (black bars). Source: catch reconstruction database of the Azores (Pham *et al.*, 2013; Fauconnet *et al.*, 2019a).

Figure 5. Annual catches of deep-water shark species in the Azores bottom longline (grey bars) and drifting deep-water longline fisheries (black bars), grouped by IUCN status (NA = Not Available). Within each IUCN group, species are ordered by increasing catches in the bottom longline fishery. Species under zero TAC/fishing prohibition are indicated by *. Catches were averaged over the 2010–2018 period; errors bars indicate standard deviation of the annual catch values (black for the bottom longline fishery; grey for the drifting longline fishery). Source: adapted from catch reconstruction database of the Azores (Pham *et al.*, 2013; Fauconnet *et al.*, 2019a).

(15.2% of total catch) per year (Machete *et al.*, 2011; Fauconnet *et al.*, 2019a; Figure 5), in which the Endangered leafscale gulper shark (*C. squamosus*) dominated the bycatch.

These levels of deep-water shark bycatch in Azorean fisheries do not surpass that of similar gears in other regions (Clarke *et al.*, 2005; Figueiredo *et al.*, 2005; Coelho and Erzini, 2008a; Bordalo-Machado *et al.*, 2009; Pajuelo *et al.*, 2010; Ramos *et al.*, 2013; Freitas *et al.*, 2018). Shark bycatch on longlines may be lower in comparison to gillnets and bottom trawls in terms of total tonnage (Connolly and Kelly, 1996; Walker *et al.*, 2005; Oliver *et al.*, 2015; Gray and Kennelly, 2018), however, proportional to the total catch, longlines tend to catch sharks that are larger, more mature and greater in number (Coelho and Erzini, 2008a; Moura *et al.*, 2018). This may be because the sharks are actively attracted to bait and

able to avoid or swim away from nets (Hareide and Garnes, 2001; Clarke *et al.*, 2002a; Coelho and Erzini, 2008a). Given the high vulnerability of deep-water sharks, even reduced by-catch levels on hook-and-line gears can constitute a conservation issue that needs to be monitored and managed effectively.

Increased fishing pressure and mounting scientific evidence indicating the vulnerability of deep-water sharks to exploitation (Garcia *et al.*, 2008; Clarke, 2009; Simpfendorfer and Kyne, 2009) prompted a series of management measures sequentially implemented by the European Commission (EC). Beginning with setting catch quotas for several deep-water shark species in 2005 (EC 2270/2004; Supplementary Table SA), the EC eventually disallowed targeted deep-water shark fisheries entirely and progressively set a Total Allowable Catch (TAC) limit of zero for deep-water sharks (EC

1359/2008; Figure 4; Supplementary Table SA). A landing requirement called the landing obligation (LO) was progressively brought into effect in European fisheries from 2015 (EU 1380/2013). The LO required the total catch of species under catch limits (TACs/quotas) to be landed and counted against fishery quotas, compelling any fishery to stop fishing upon reaching the quota of the most limiting species. Applied as such, zero TAC species such as deep-water sharks would act as “choke” species, triggering a premature shut-down of the fishery with potentially strong negative socio-economic consequences. This hypothetical scenario incentivized efforts to identify ways to avoid unwanted catch and increase survival of deep-water sharks, particularly since a survival exemption could be granted under the LO if scientifically proven a species had high potential survivability (EU 1380/2013); exemption that would allow the discard of unwanted catch without triggering a fishery shutdown. However, the LO only started to be implemented from 2019 in the Azores, and before this scenario could materialize, the zero TAC was abolished by the EC and deep-water sharks turned into prohibited species (EU 2018/2025), meaning that all deep-water sharks caught by any European fishing vessels were to be immediately released at sea and not landed. The fishing prohibition itself has not been an incentive for fishers to avoid catching deep-water sharks as they can simply release or discard this catch without further repercussions. Hence, regardless of the changes in legislation through the years, fishing practices have remained largely unchanged.

Effective monitoring and management of deep-water shark bycatch is obstructed by the fact that most species are data poor. Many universal knowledge gaps remain, including the understanding of basic biological and ecological traits of several species, the consequences of reduction in deep-water shark populations on the health of deep-sea ecosystems and the economic impacts of deep-water shark depredation on hook-and-line fisheries. Despite being a conservation concern, deep-water shark bycatch remains poorly studied and catch data that are essential to estimate bycatch amounts and compositions are mostly scarce. The fishing prohibition implemented in European fisheries inherently hinders data collection and accurate estimation of derived bycatch amounts. Since no landing is allowed nor recorded, no data exists on the continued capture of deep-water sharks except for limited onboard observer records. As in many European countries (Uhlmann *et al.*, 2014), the onboard observer coverage of the Portuguese fleet fishing in the Azores EEZ is limited to a small portion of fishing vessels and effort (Machete *et al.*, 2011; Pham *et al.*, 2013; Fauconnet *et al.*, 2019a). The low coverage is especially pronounced in the Azorean bottom hook-and-line fisheries that are dominated by small vessels (Carvalho *et al.*, 2011) with little space to carry scientific personnel (Machete *et al.*, 2020) and widely dispersed among the nine islands of the archipelago. In 2021, the regional onboard observers programme covered 1.4% of the fishing trips of bottom longliners and 0.3% of the trips of handliners, 13.7 and 5.3% of the total number of fishing vessels respectively (D. Reis, pers. comm.). Even regional fisheries monitoring surveys contribute minimally to the information required to infer stock status (Santos *et al.*, 2020). Thus, population status estimates are difficult to obtain for such data-poor stocks, the absence of which raises doubts regarding the sustainability of deep-water shark bycatch in local fisheries.

Challenges in avoiding deep-water sharks in the Azores: species ecology

To begin with, the high diversity of deep-water sharks in the Azores by itself constitutes a challenge to bycatch avoidance. The large number of species with diverse behaviours make it difficult to identify a one-size-fits-all management solution to avoid unwanted catches (Favaro and Côté, 2013; Reinhardt *et al.*, 2018; Gilman *et al.*, 2019). Deep-water sharks of the Azores can occur along a large gradient of depths, from the surface (e.g., kitefin shark *D. licha*, leafscale gulper shark *C. squamosus*) to 4500 m depth (great lanternshark *E. princeps*; Table 1; Figure 2; Ebert and Dando, 2021), and several species are known to perform diel vertical migrations (Rodríguez-Cabello *et al.*, 2016). Some species may migrate long distances (Catarino *et al.*, 2015; Rodríguez-Cabello *et al.*, 2016), while others appear to be resident in the Azores (Fontes *et al.*, 2015).

The 25 species differ greatly in the abundance in which they are found in the Azores: while ten species are considered common, inferred from regional fishery-dependent and fishing survey data, seven are occasional, and eight are rare or very rare (Figure 2; Fauconnet *et al.*, 2020). The Azores dogfish (*S. garricki*) is an extreme case of this rarity, as only two specimens are known, both caught at depths that are commonly utilized by local fisheries (Kukuev and Konovalenko, 1988; Kukuev, 2006). It remains unknown whether this species is mostly pelagic, and hence potentially out of reach of local fisheries, or mostly demersal and more likely to be caught by local fishers. To complicate matters further, there is a possibility that *S. garricki* is unreported or misidentified since it is largely unfamiliar in the region. The absence of biological and ecological information for rare species makes it difficult to assess threats or suggest bycatch avoidance measures. On the other hand, data available for the more common species to support development of better-suited management measures remains insufficient to assess population status (ICES, 2020b; Santos *et al.*, 2020) or the extent to which bycatch threatens their conservation.

Correctly identifying species is another obstacle in the study of deep-water sharks, with persisting taxonomic uncertainties and recurrent misidentification within species complexes (Iglésias *et al.*, 2010; Straube *et al.*, 2011; Catarino *et al.*, 2020). Many deep-water sharks, particularly within the genus *Deania*, *Centrophorus*, *Centroscyttus*, and *Etmopterus* are very similar and easily misidentified (Moura *et al.*, 2008; Veríssimo *et al.*, 2014; Fauconnet *et al.*, 2020; ICES, 2020b). Even unrelated species can often be difficult to differentiate, such as the roughskin dogfish *C. owstonii* and velvet dogfish *Z. squamulosus*. Inaccurate species identification and incorrect catch reporting at species level by both fisheries observers and scientists can potentially put species at risk by masking divergent abundance trends of similar looking species, and has proven to be an impediment in defining conservation measures (Dulvy *et al.*, 2000; Iglésias *et al.*, 2010). It is also not surprising that the taxonomy of deep-water sharks continues to undergo corrections and clarifications (e.g., Stefanni *et al.*, 2021) and new species are regularly discovered (e.g., Ebert *et al.*, 2021b).

Regional identification manuals encourage better species identification and accurate catch reporting (e.g., AFMA, 2015; FAO, 2015; Ebert *et al.*, 2021a), to which end a deep-water shark identification manual was developed for the Azores (Fauconnet *et al.*, 2020). The manual was primarily directed

towards local fishers and fisheries observers. It describes each species of deep-water shark known to occur in the region and provides simple external characteristics to help distinguish any given species from another. A dichotomous key using easy-to-identify distinctive characteristics was built to further facilitate species identification. Ecological and biological data are displayed for each species to communicate their biodiversity and vulnerability (Fauconnet *et al.*, 2020). The manual hopes to increase the accuracy of data reporting and raise awareness among the fishers about the vulnerability of deep-water sharks. It has recently begun to be distributed to local fishers, but has not yet seen widespread use.

Avoiding deep-water sharks in the Azores: tactical measures

Tactical choices made by fishers on “where, when, and how” to fish play a central role in avoiding unwanted catch (Dunn *et al.*, 2011; Mortensen *et al.*, 2018; Reid *et al.*, 2019; Uhlmann *et al.*, 2019). Spatial management measures in particular are widely used to reduce unwanted catch and manage bycatch (Dunn *et al.*, 2011; Pérez Roda *et al.*, 2019). Even though spatial measures are frequently implemented through a top-down regulatory approach, it is now well known that participatory bottom-up approaches with incentive-based solutions are more promising to successfully address bycatch problems (Rochet *et al.*, 2014). Fisheries management initiatives should provide incentives to encourage fishers to avoid unwanted catch (Condie *et al.*, 2014; Rochet *et al.*, 2014; Little *et al.*, 2015; Uhlmann *et al.*, 2019). For example, charts identifying areas where unwanted species have historically been caught or recorded in high abundance can be used as a decision-support tool for fishers to select which areas to safely fish or which to avoid altogether (Reid *et al.*, 2019).

To identify these critical areas in the Azores, distribution models were developed to predict the presence of 15 deep-water elasmobranchs within the Exclusive Economic Zone of the Azores Archipelago up to 2000 m depth (Reid *et al.*, 2019; Das *et al.*, 2022). The species modeled included 12 sharks and 3 skates that were most frequently caught in the fishery-independent scientific demersal longline survey, combined with fishery-dependent observer data obtained aboard commercial bottom longline vessels, over 20 years (1996–2017 for the surveys, 2004–2018 for the observer data). The predicted areas of high probability of presence, abundance, as well as habitat overlap between different species theoretically can be used to help fishers avoid unwanted bycatch of deep-water sharks.

The models identified that bottom depth had the greatest environmental influence on the probability of occurrence for 15 species and abundance for the six most common species. Nine of the 15 species studied (thornback ray *Raja clavata*, tope shark *Galeorhinus galeus*, common skate *Dipturus batis* complex, shagreen ray *Leucoraja fullonica*, kitefin shark *D. licha*, velvet belly *E. spinax*, spined pygmy shark *S. laticaudus*, smooth lanternshark *E. pusillus*, and arrowhead dogfish *D. profundorum*) were found to peak in occurrence and abundance in depths ≤ 800 m (Das *et al.*, 2022), spatially overlapping with the distribution of commercially important teleost species (Parra *et al.*, 2017) and with deep-water bottom-fishing effort (Diogo *et al.*, 2015). Three species (birdbeak dogfish *D. calcea*, leafscale gulper shark *C. squamosus* and longnose velvet dogfish *C. crepidater*) were found to peak in

occurrence in areas with bottom depth of around 1200 m. Spatial overlap of these species with fisheries is possible but limited as local fishers rarely fish at these depths (Diogo *et al.*, 2015). The three remaining species (roughskin dogfish *C. owstonii*, Portuguese dogfish *C. coelelepis*, and great lanternshark *E. princeps*) peak in probability of occurrence at depths over 1200 m, hence minimal interactions with local fisheries are expected (Das *et al.*, 2022). Thus, for this last group of three species, depth-based spatial limits that would impede fisheries to extend into depths over 1200 m, may be a simple but effective avoidance strategy, as recognized by local fishers (Fauconnet *et al.*, 2019b) and supported by scientific evidence (Clarke *et al.*, 2015).

In contrast, depth-based spatial limits are not a viable strategy for species occurring regularly within the same operating range of bottom longlines. Alternative approaches such as habitat-based spatial management measures also need to be considered (Wiegand *et al.*, 2011; Giménez *et al.*, 2020; Garbett *et al.*, 2021), even though they may also overlap with the distribution of commercial fish species (Parra *et al.*, 2017). Models of deep-water elasmobranch distribution identified distinctive geological features, such as seamounts and ridges, as areas where the probability of presence of most species overlapped (Das *et al.*, 2022). Results that account for habitat features in combination with depth can therefore indicate candidate features to inform area-based management (Clark and Dunn, 2012) to avoid and reduce unwanted catches, especially of highly resident species (Daley *et al.*, 2015). In contrast, species migrating over large spaces (Catarino *et al.*, 2015; Rodríguez-Cabello *et al.*, 2016) or vertically migrating on a daily or seasonal basis, such as the kitefin shark *D. licha* or the leafscale gulper shark *C. squamosus* (Klippel *et al.*, 2016; Rodríguez-Cabello *et al.*, 2016; P. Afonso, unpublished data), may not be effectively avoided using fisheries management measures based on area or depth limits. Moreover, the habitat use of many species is still not completely understood, further limiting the relevance of spatial measures. Additional measures like gear restrictions or adaptations can hence improve avoidance of deep-water sharks catches where depth-based and area-based limits may not be effective (Williams *et al.*, 2016; Fauconnet *et al.*, 2019b). These models provide promising results but require ground-truthing to be a viable bycatch avoidance and decision support tool.

Avoiding deep-water sharks in the Azores: technical measures

Improving gear selectivity through technical adaptations is another obvious way fishers can avoid unwanted catch (O'Neill *et al.*, 2019; Uhlmann *et al.*, 2019). Gear type has a significant influence on bycatch due to the different modes of operation and fishing selectivity. Regional distribution model outputs for some species indicate that the probability of occurrence, i.e., the probability of capture, of elasmobranchs in the Azores is lower on the local vertical handlines *gorazeira* than on the bottom longlines (Das *et al.*, 2022). Handlines operate with short soak times, fewer hooks, and at shallower depths, using a lighter tackle that can be easily bitten off by the sharks (Fauconnet *et al.*, 2019b). These attributes contribute to a greater probability of post-release survival of elasmobranchs caught on handlines compared to longlines (Ellis *et al.*, 2017). Local fishers too concur that not only is deep-water shark bycatch higher on longlines, but deep-water elasmobranchs retrieved

on longlines suffer higher at-vessel mortality than on handlines (Fauconnet *et al.*, 2019b). Switching from longlining to handlining could thus be a straightforward way to reduce deep-water shark bycatch and mortality. This switch is already occurring in the fishery since handlines are more cost-effective than longlines given the lower expenses, even if the catch of target species by handlines tends to be lower and less diverse than with longlines (Fauconnet *et al.*, 2019b). Handline gears, with both reduced bycatch of deep-water sharks and improved survival, have been identified elsewhere as the gear with potential to provide a compromise between species conservation and continuation of the important socio-economic fishing activity, even within protected areas (Daley *et al.*, 2015; Williams *et al.*, 2016).

Sharks are one of the main bycatches on longlines because larger species and specimens have larger feeding ranges and are more successful in competing for bait (Løkkeborg and Bjordal, 1992). In pelagic longline fisheries, a wide range of bycatch reduction devices have been tested to specifically avoid vulnerable species such as pelagic sharks (Gilman *et al.*, 2008), sea turtles (Gilman *et al.*, 2006; Read, 2007), seabirds (Løkkeborg, 2011), or to more generally avoid all non-commercially valuable catch (Gilman *et al.*, 2016, 2018). A limited number of experiments have been undertaken for bottom longline fisheries to avoid bycatch of demersal elasmobranchs (Afonso *et al.*, 2011; Favaro and Côté, 2013), and only few specifically apply to deep-water sharks (Coelho *et al.*, 2003; Ramos *et al.*, 2013). For example, Coelho *et al.* (2003) found that positioning hooks farther from the seafloor had strong potential to reduce the catch of deep-water sharks on demersal stone-buoy longlines, with limited effect on the catch of target species. This is corroborated by the success in using floats to suspend demersal longlines in the water column where they are less likely to be encountered by demersal sharks and rays (Afonso *et al.*, 2011). However, this approach remains understudied and requires further testing (Favaro and Côté, 2013). Similarly, the use of nylon leaders instead of wire leaders that are too strong to be cut by sharks also remains understudied (Favaro and Côté, 2013) despite being proven effective in reducing shark bycatch in pelagic longlines (Ward *et al.*, 2008). Results from Ramos *et al.* (2013) suggest lower bycatch of deep-water sharks on nylon leaders compared to wire leaders, but are inconclusive due to insufficient sample size.

Alternative measures, such as electromagnetic exclusion devices, acoustic or light-based deterrents should be investigated, as advised by ICES (ICES, 2020a). The unique sensibility of elasmobranchs to detect electromagnetic fields through their ampullae of Lorenzini (Kalmijn, 1971) instigates an aversion response to electropositive metals or magnets in various species. This sensory system has been leveraged to test the efficacy of electropositive and magnetic repellents in recent years (Kaimmer and Stoner, 2008; Brill *et al.*, 2009; O'Connell *et al.*, 2011, 2014; Richards *et al.*, 2018), with results differing between shark species. Some studies suggest up to a 60% reduction in the capture of pelagic and coastal sharks on longlines with these repellents (O'Connell *et al.*, 2011; O'Connell *et al.*, 2014; Richards *et al.*, 2018). However, to our knowledge this methodology has never been tested on deep-water sharks. If proven efficient, the use of electrosensory repellents could reduce the bycatch of deep-water sharks as well as contribute to lower shark-induced catch depredation and fishing

Figure 6. Effect of hook type on deep-water shark catch, based on fishing experiments carried out onboard a professional longline fishing vessel. Source: Fauconnet *et al.* in prep.

gear damage, hence reducing economic losses. Yet, the high cost of these metals and the rapid corrosion in seawater leading to loss of efficiency, has deterred widespread application in commercial fisheries (Favaro and Côté, 2013).

Alternatively, circle hooks have been widely tested in pelagic longline fisheries and have delivered promising results in reducing bycatch mortality of pelagic sharks and sea turtles (Read, 2007; Godin *et al.*, 2012; Reinhardt *et al.*, 2018), though catchability varies by species. Due to their closed shape, circle hooks tend to lodge at or close to the mouth as opposed to J-hooks that easily become embedded in the digestive tract (Carruthers *et al.*, 2009; Pacheco *et al.*, 2011; Godin *et al.*, 2012). Individuals caught on circle hooks are thus more likely to survive (Kerstetter and Graves, 2006), reducing the lethal effects of pelagic longlines even if not necessarily reducing the risk of capture. To our knowledge, the comparative effects of circle versus J-hooks on deep-water shark catch had not been tested until 2018 when it was first investigated in the Azores. Fishing experiments on deep-water bottom longlines with alternating circle and J-hooks were used to compare the catchability, hooking position and condition of captured individuals (L. Fauconnet, unpublished data). Data from onboard observers suggest that the results for J-hooks are comparable between the fishing experiments and the commercial bottom longline fishery. The results of the fishing experiments suggested that contrary to what has been found for sea turtles and pelagic sharks (Read, 2007; Godin *et al.*, 2012; Reinhardt *et al.*, 2018), circle hooks are not an effective way to mitigate bycatch of deep-water sharks. Circle hooks performed worse, i.e., similar proportion of gut-hooking and at-vessel mortality but higher catch rates, than the J-hooks currently used by commercial longlines (L. Fauconnet, unpublished data; Figure 6). These results also constituted the first estimates of at-vessel mortality of deep-water sharks in the Azores. At-vessel mortality levels observed with circle hooks in the Azores were of a similar order of magnitude, or even slightly lower for some species of deep-water sharks, than a longline survey using circle hooks carried out in northern Spain (El Cachucho Marine Protected Area, NE Atlantic; Rodríguez-Cabello and Sánchez, 2017).

Onboard handling practices too contribute significantly to post-capture vitality, ergo post-release survival, of deep-water sharks. Data collected by observers onboard Azorean com-

Figure 7. Effect of handling practices on the vitality state of deep-water sharks caught on-board professional bottom longline fishing vessels, based on observer data (2017–2018). Labels indicate absolute numbers of individuals. Handling was considered “bad” when the shark beat against the boat or was left alive in a box or on deck before being released, and considered “good” if no manipulation compromising the individual’s survival was registered.

mercial longliners showed that in addition to deep-hooking, higher at-vessel mortality of individuals was strongly correlated to bad handling practices. Individuals that were beaten or hurt during capture or left on deck before being released were significantly more likely to be dead or moribund compared to those handled using “good” practices (Figure 7). To encourage better handling practices and potentially higher post-release survival, a diagrammatic guide was included in the deep-water shark species identification manual for longline fishers (Fauconnet *et al.*, 2020). The handling practices were also summarised as a poster and distributed to local fishers. This included a description of morphologically sensitive points, advice on how to handle and transport sharks during the whole fishing operation (hauling, hook removal, treatment on deck) and how to properly release the animals, highlighting the “dos and don’ts”. Given the range of sizes of deep-water sharks caught by the fishery, the guide included separate handling practices for individuals of small and medium lengths, similar to the manual for tuna purse-seine fisheries developed by Poisson *et al.* (2012, 2014). The manual and poster have been distributed to Azorean fishers to incentivize better handling practices that favour the survival of individuals caught in the fishery.

While a common technical modification of switching to circle hooks showed little success in mitigating unwanted catch and mortality of deep-water sharks in the Azores, several measures including incentivizing the use of handlines over longlines, raising bottom longline hooks off the seafloor, and using nylon leaders require further testing to conclusively prove their efficacy. Additionally, better handling practices of captured individuals requires widespread adoption to alleviate the bycatch mortality on deep-water demersal fisheries.

Challenges with incentivizing fishers to avoid deep-water sharks

In addition to the tactical and technical challenges inherent to bottom longline fisheries, the fishers’ personal incentive in avoiding deep-water shark bycatch poses a challenge in

the Azores. Interviews carried out with Azorean fishers highlighted that around 30% of the interviewees frequently caught deep-water sharks as bycatch (Table 2), and many argued they are difficult to avoid (Fauconnet *et al.*, 2019b). Several fishers declared they actively avoid deep-water sharks, by avoiding fishing at certain depths and times of the day, particularly at night. Many of the fishers interviewed were unwilling to avoid deep-water sharks and expressed discontent at not being allowed to fish them. They claimed that the abundance of the sharks was too high, which according to them, creates an imbalance in the ecosystem and negatively impacts their fishing (Fauconnet *et al.*, 2019b). Deep-water sharks were frequently blamed for damaging deep-water longline fishing gear and depredating or scaring off commercially valuable demersal fishes (Fauconnet *et al.*, 2019a, 2019b).

Fishers’ willingness to avoid deep-water sharks is further impeded by a strong economic incentive to retain sharks for liver oil, and potential use of the sharks as bait. Squalene extracted from shark liver oil remains in great demand and is highly profitable, with the market valued at 212 million USD (Fagundes *et al.*, 2019; Chandra *et al.*, 2021). The global demand for squalene comes from the cosmetic industry, and finds increasing applications in the pharmaceutical and nutraceutical industries (Lozano-Grande *et al.*, 2018; Macdonald and Soll, 2020; Chandra *et al.*, 2021). Squalene is widely used as an antioxidant and as an adjuvant in vaccines (Chandra *et al.*, 2021), and has increasing roles as an anticancer and anti-inflammatory agent, creating a strong demand for this substance (Fagundes *et al.*, 2019). Although traditionally, deep-water shark liver oil is the richest source of squalene, efforts to develop biotechnological methods of squalene production have been increasing because its extraction conflicts with species conservation (Ghimire *et al.*, 2016; Chandra *et al.*, 2021; Potijun *et al.*, 2021). Promising results have been achieved using microorganisms such as cyanobacteria, which has been demonstrated to be able to stand out as squalene producer, representing a renewable source with higher production rates during the entire year and a short time-period to acquire the compound (Fagundes *et al.*, 2019). Despite recent progress in the manufacture of squalene from alternate sources, deep-water shark liver oil continues to be the most common form of squalene isolated for supplemental use by the pharmaceutical industry (Fagundes *et al.*, 2019). Currently over 50% of global squalene is estimated to come from deep-water sharks (around 6 million individuals) to meet annual industry demand (Chandra *et al.*, 2021). The market constitutes an obstacle to the avoidance of deep-water shark bycatch. To date, despite the fishing prohibition, some fishers still express the will to exploit deep-water shark liver oil to meet this demand. The difficult species identification complicates the enforcement of this measure. Implementing a rigorous control of the squalene market to avoid extraction from a prohibited species, could help limit the harvest of deep-water sharks.

Considering the challenges in incentivizing fishers to avoid bycatch of deep-water sharks, it is essential to involve them in the process. Further research, including integration of fishers ecological knowledge, needs to be carried out with a close collaboration between fishers and scientists. It is with the support of fishers and complementary knowledge, promoting a cooperative approach, that effective bycatch mitigation measures can be identified and successfully implemented (Rochet *et al.*, 2014; Gaspare *et al.*, 2015; Abreu *et al.*, 2017).

Table 2. Summary of responses concerning bycatch, uses, and handling of deep-water sharks (DWS) by bottom hook-and-line fishers.

	Catch of DWS				Use of DWS				Handling of DWS		
	Yes	Rare	No	NA	DIS	LAN	Bait	NA	Cut	Rm.	NA
Longline	5	3	1	1	5	2	1	2	1	2	6
Handline	2	6	3	0	6	1	0	4	3	2	7
% of answers	33.3%	42.9%	19.0%	4.8%	52.4%	14.3%	4.8%	28.6%	19.0%	19.0%	61.9%

NA is no answer, DIS is discard, LAN is landing, Cut is cut the line, Rm. is remove the hook before releasing the shark. Source: Fauconnet *et al.* (2019b).

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Supplementary Data

Supplementary material is available at the *ICESJMS* online.

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Authors contribution statement

LF, TM, and PA conceptualized the idea and designed the work. LF wrote the first draft of the manuscript. All authors provided data essential for the review and the analyses, and contributed to iterative discussions, and writing of the manuscript.

Data Availability Statement

No new data was generated for this review paper.

Conflict of interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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